

Pediatric Open Supracondylar Humeral Fractures: Insights from a Single-Center Experience in a Developing Nation

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: This abstract summarizes three pediatric cases involving cubital injuries caused by falls. These cases highlight the significance of immediate assessment and comprehensive management.

Results: In Case I, a preschooler child (3-5years) presented with a laceration and exposed bone and type 4 supracondylar humerus fracture, requiring ATLS protocols, wound care, and surgical intervention. Case II involved a school-aged child (6-12 years) with a similar injury, emphasizing the importance of early vascular assessment and collaboration. Case III, a toddler (1-3 years), had arterial insufficiency detected via Doppler ultrasound, leading to successful surgical repair.

Conclusion: These cases underscore the critical role of timely intervention and interdisciplinary cooperation in optimizing outcomes for pediatric cubital injuries.

Keywords: Pediatric Trauma; Cubital Injury; Surgical Intervention; Multidisciplinary Collaboration; Pediatric Orthopedics

INTRODUCTION

An open supracondylar humeral fracture is a fracture involving the distal humerus immediately above the elbow. Children commonly sustain distal humerus supracondylar fractures, which make up about 3% of all fractures and 55% to 80% of elbow fractures. One percent of these supracondylar fractures have open wounds.^[1] Given the proximity of the fracture to the radial, median, and anterior interosseous nerves, as well as the brachial artery with extension displacement fractures, there is a risk of neurovascular injury.^[2] Infection, compartment syndrome, and nonunion are often also more likely with open fractures.^[3]

CASE PRESENTATION I

A preschooler child (3-5years) presented to the emergency department after falling down stairs. After applying the Advanced Traumatic Life Support protocol, she was examined thoroughly. There was a lacerated wound in the left cubital region; bone seemed to protrude from the wound, as shown in **Figure [1a]**. Distal radial and ulnar arteries were feeble. Patient was resuscitated, and the wound was washed thoroughly. Portable X-rays were taken (for documentation purposes) in between, as shown in **Figure [1b]**. Bone was reduced, back slab was given, and distal pulses were palpable. Preoperative preparation was checked, and the patient was shifted to OT, in which open reduction was done through the extension of the wound, K wire passed in a cross manner, and the brachial artery was intact and pulsatile. The vascular team on board cleared the case after surgery. After 2 weeks, stitches were removed, and after 3 weeks, wires were removed, and the range of motion exercises were started back slab given during sleeping hours. It was discontinued 1 week later.

Figure 1A:

Figure 1B:

Figure 1C

Figure: 1A showing open fracture of Left humerus, 1B and 1C denotes Lateral and A.P view with Gartlant supracondylar type VI fracture, 1D indicates post-fixation with cross k wires lateral view.

CASE PRESENTATION II

A school-aged child (6-12 years) presented to the emergency department after falling from his crib. After following the ATLS protocol examination, there was a large wound up to 5 into 8cm large at the cubital region; the bone was exposed from the wound as shown in [Figure \[2a\]](#), distal pulses were a feeble thorough washout with normal saline, and povidone-iodine was performed. Meanwhile, x-rays were taken at the resuscitation bay, as shown in [Figure \[2b\]](#), bone reduction was done, and the wound was approximated. A back slab was given, and a capillary refill was less than 2 seconds after reduction, and the patient was sent for resuscitation and IV antibiotics and painkillers. After resuscitation, x-rays were taken vascular surgery team was taken on board, attendants counselled, preoperative preparation was done, and the patient was shifted to OT where wound assessment was done, debridement of the wound was done there was an intact vascular network as assessed through a wound in the cubital region. 2 K wires of 1.8mm were passed from medial and lateral condyles of the humerus in crisscross manner as shown in the [Figure \[2c\]](#). Post-operative vascular status was found to be normal, with triphasic flow in both radial and ulnar arteries on hand held doppler. The patient was discharged after two days with a follow-up visit card.

CASE PRESENTATION III

A toddler (1-3 years) patient presented to the Accident and Emergency Department after falling down the stairs. After following the ATLS protocol examination, there was a large wound up to 3 to 6cm large at the cubital region; the bone was exposed from the wound as shown in [Figure \[3a\]](#), distal pulses were feeble, thorough washout with normal saline and povidone-iodine was performed. Meanwhile, x-rays were taken at the resuscitation bay as shown in [Figure \[3c\]](#), bone reduction was done, the wound was approximated, the back slab was given, and

capillary refill was more than 2 seconds after reduction, and the patient was sent for resuscitation and IV antibiotics and painkillers and Doppler ultrasound. Ultrasound findings showed moderate arterial insufficiency in both radial and ulnar arteries. After resuscitation, x-rays were taken, the vascular surgery team was taken on board, attendants counselled, preoperative preparation was done, and the patient was shifted to OT, where wound assessment was done and wound debridement was done. The brachial artery was completely lacerated, as shown in the [Figure \[3b\]](#). The bone was fixed with K wires of 1.8mm, as shown in [Figure \[3c\]](#), and the vascular team did reverse greater saphenous vein graft back slab was given. The post-operative vascular status seemed to be intact. The patient was discharged after 2 days with a follow-up visit card.

Figure 2 showing case II, 2A denotes open wound with visible fracture bone, 2B is Lateral view showing type VI injury, 2C are Lateral and A.P views post-reduction with K-wires.

Figure 2A:

Figure 2B:

Figure 2C:

Figure 3A:

Figure 3B:

Figure 3C

Figure 3D

Figure 3: Showing case III, 3A denotes open wound with visible fracture bone and 3B shows after repair of brachial artery with venous graft, 3C is A.P view showing type VI injury, 3D are Lateral and A.P views post-reduction with K-wires.

Table 1: Modified Gartland Classification of Supracondylar Fractures

Parameter	Case I	Case II	Case III
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Age	Preschooler	School age child	Toddler
Mechanism of Injury	Fall from stairs	Fall from cradle	Fall from stairs
Wound Size	Lacerated, bone exposed (4x4cm)	Large (5x8cm), bone exposed	Large (3x6cm), bone exposed
Distal Pulses	Feeble	Feeble	Feeble
Initial Management	ATLS protocol, resuscitation, wound cleaning, portable x-rays	ATLS protocol, wound cleaning, x-rays, bone reduction, wound closure	ATLS protocol, wound cleaning, x-rays, bone reduction, wound closure
Post-Reduction Capillary Refill	< 2 seconds	< 2 seconds	> 2 seconds
Additional Diagnostics	IV antibiotics, painkillers, Doppler ultrasound	IV antibiotics, painkillers, Doppler ultrasound	IV antibiotics, painkillers, Doppler ultrasound
Vascular Assessment	Brachial artery intact	Intact vascular network confirmed	Complete brachial artery laceration

Table 2. Patient characteristics

Outcome	Case I	Case II	Case III
Pain and Discomfort	None	Slight	None
Range of Motion (Flexion)	136	129	121
Range of Motion (Extension)	1	1	0
Range of Motion (Pronation and supination)	90	90	85
Strength	Good	Good	Good
Neurovascular Status	Adequate	Adequate	Adequate
Wound Healing	Good	Average	Good
Orthopedic Imaging	No deformity	No deformty	No deformity
Complications	None	None	None
Growth Plate Assessment (Pediatric)	None	None	None

DISCUSSION

The literature evident numerous potential complications associated with open SCF, suggesting a significant association of complications with the course of the management. Approximately half of the open SCFs involve nerve damage, and 10-20% are associated with absent or reduced pulses.^[2] Open SCFs result in longer hospital stays, ipsilateral forearm fractures, and a higher incidence of neurovascular complications escalating the need for vascular procedures.^[4] Skaggs et al. reported a 3% post-fracture infection rate associated with open SCFs.^[5] The higher incidence of complications and challenging management courses necessitate prompt reduction and surgical stabilization.^[6] Literature suggested superior clinical and radiological outcomes in open SCF when managed with reduction with direct visualization and manipulation, however, the absolute management strategy is conflicted. Access to the fracture site is frequently improved following irrigation, debridement, and neurovascular decompression.^[6,7]

We discussed 3 cases of open SCFs in the pediatric population to exemplify the challenges and management strategies. We employed the modified Gartland classification for image grading and addressing the type and severity of the fractures.^[8,9]

Dulgeroglu et al. highlighted a case of open SCF associated with neurovascular injury and infection, managed with irrigation, debridement, and open reduction with 2 lateral and 1 medial K-wires.^[10] Similarly, our 3rd case

highlights a toddler with open SCF with feeble distal pulses detected as arterial insufficiency, necessitating the need for vascular team intervention. The brachial artery was completely lacerated, however, timely grafting with greater saphenous nerve and orthopedic intervention employing the 1.8mm K-wires to reduce the fracture and applying backslap. The timely management showed significant post-operative improvement with intact vascular status.

Boukhentiche et al. presented an extensive literature review to address the course of management in open SCFs management to highlight the controversial role of K-wire in the management of SCFs, however, supporting the K-wire in their case management, showing excellent improvement in clinical and radiological outcomes assessed using Flynn's criteria,^[11] consistent with the principle published by Stewart et al.^[8] Carrazzone et al. supported the crossed K-wire approach as more effective for the reduction of surgically managed SCFs.^[12] However, Sankar et al. published a series of 322 Gartland type III fractures managed with K-wire, the author reported an inconclusive result secondary to the loss of fixation secondary to technical errors.^[13]

We used crossed K-wires for the management of all three cases, showing clinically significant improvement in follow-up consistent with Carrazzone et al.^[13] Our studies highlighted the potential significance of immediate ATLS protocol, wound care, and surgical intervention, emphasizing early vascular assessment and collaboration between intervening surgical teams. These cases underscore the critical role of timely intervention and interdisciplinary cooperation in optimizing outcomes for open SCFs and showing improved clinical outcomes employing crossed K-wire technique. Managing these fractures involves addressing potential complications, such as nerve and vascular damage, and minimizing the risk of infection.

CONCLUSION

Open SHFs are rare, however, the management is particularly challenging. We address three cases of open SHFs to report the significance of prompt assessment, wound care, and the role of crossed K-wire for the reduction. Neurovascular compromise is a potential complication of open SHFs, therefore, we support early detection, and fostering collaboration among different medical specialties is required to achieve excellent results.

Type	Description
I	Undisplaced
II	Displaced in one plane
III	Displaced in 2 or 3 plane
IV	Complete periosteal disruption with instability in flexion and extension

Ethical Approval: IRB was received from the institution.

Consent to Participate: The consent to publish the patient's data including images was taken from the patient's guardian. We are grateful to the patient and her attendants for granting consent to share her data publicly.

Consent to Publish: We agree to transfer the copyrights after acceptance of our manuscript.

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